

ACTIVITIES OF REPRESENTATIVES OF THE KOREAN PEOPLE FORCIBLY DISPLACED IN THE 1930S - 1940S IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF THE TASHKENT REGION: PROBLEMS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8395489>

Abstract. *The Korean invasion of Uzbekistan on the eve of World War II in connection with the policy of forced resettlement - deportation of entire peoples, which began in the USSR. For peoples who were forced to be displaced, this policy was a real tragedy. Forced displacement policies resulted in a huge number of casualties, moral and political losses. Great damage was done to the culture and economy of the Peoples condemned to eviction. In this article, the representatives of the Korean people who worked in the agricultural sector of the Tashkent region were presented: information about the problem and achievements.*

Keywords: *korean people, "evacuation", "Polyarnaya zvezda", Sovet of people's commissars of the SSSR, deportation, forced relocation.*

INTRODUCTION

After the deportation of Koreans to Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan in 1937, a large proportion of Koreans in Kistan gathered in kolkhozes and sovkhoses and engaged in farming activities. One of the reasons for this was that the distribution of new labor resources was something evidence confirming that it was due to the forced nature of deportation and the corresponding nature of the settlement, many Koreans, working in fishing, mining in the Far East, intellectual-technological or other industries rah, could not find work in their specialty. Further early advances in the form of a significant cause were made in March 1938, when grain was given only to collective farmers.

The Korean invasion of Uzbekistan on the eve of World War II began in the USSR in connection with the policy of forced resettlement - deportation of entire peoples. For peoples who were forced to be displaced, this policy was a real tragedy. Forced displacement policies resulted in a huge number of casualties, moral and political losses. Great damage was done to the culture and economy of the Peoples condemned to eviction.

The "evacuation" of those sentenced to displacement became a real tragedy for these peoples.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

On August 21, 1937, the Soviet of people's commissars of the SSSR and the Political Bureau of the Bolshevik KP MK issued a decree on the relocation of Koreans from the Far East to Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, which provided for the relocation of all Koreans living in the border regions of the Far East to the regions of the South Kazakhstan region, Islet districts, Balkhash and the Uzbek SSR. The move was set to be completed at a speed of on January 1, 1938

Although the decree obliges the councils of the people's commissars of the Kazakh SSR and the Uzbek SSR to promptly mark resettlement areas and points, and to ensure the economic development of the displaced population to new places, to establish measures to provide them with

the necessary assistance, the adoption of this decision without agreement with the leaders of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan caused great difficulties in the implementation of the decision.

In 1937, more than 170,000 Koreans were forcibly resettled in Central Asia and Kazakhstan. More than 74,000 of them were brought to Uzbekistan and the rest to Kazakhstan, while violating the constitutional rights of the Korean people to free development, an illegal act of terrible cruelty was carried out contrary to the national policy declared by the state.

The party-state directive of August 21, 1937, in an extremely short time, imposed the governments of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan on the obligation to ensure the “economic development of the population displaced to new places” (Article 7).

The Central Asian Soviet republics, economically weakened by the collectivization policy, took on the heavy burden of accommodating many thousands of Korean families who arrived at their isolated settlements on the eve of the cold winter of 1937-1938.

This event, which is of a military-strategic nature, has dramatically changed the fate of entire peoples, is hurriedly carried out without any preparation for it. With plans to move 6,000 families (30,000 people) to Uzbekistan, the number was increased to another 5,000 families (22-25, 000 people) in October. Responsibility for the resettlement of displaced persons was assigned to the Soviets of people's commissars of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan.

This decision created many complex tasks for Uzbekistan. Materially-technically, he was not ready to receive such a large number of transplants. In the mid-1930s, the Republic had one of the last places in the country in terms of its socio-economic development.

He could not provide normal socio-economic and living conditions not only for the displaced population, but also for his own. There was a lack of housing, food, because construction materials, bread, meat were brought to Uzbekistan from other republics, there was a lack of medical personnel, medicines. In those years, malaria was in full swing in the country. According to the number of doctors per 10 thousand inhabitants (4.7 doctors), Uzbekistan ranked tenth among other republics of the Republic.

Nevertheless, the Uzbek government and people put all their effort into accepting, accommodating, food and employment of all displaced persons under those harsh conditions.

In order to implement the decision of the Soviet of people's commissars of the USSR and the Political Bureau of the Bolshevik KP MK of August 21, 1937, the Council of people's commissars of the Uzbek SSR adopted the resolution “on the displacement of Korean households” on September 16, 1937. The Republican Emergency Commission for the reception and resettlement of emigrants was formed.

The decision set out vital measures for the placement of forcibly evicted Koreans, the timely implementation of which could have a positive effect on the life of the evicted. But it was very difficult to do this in the conditions of this period.

According to the decision of the Council of people's commissars of the Uzbek SSR “on the relocation of Korean households” on September 16, 1937, 6000 Korean farms were allocated to the districts of Upper, Middle, Gurlan district and Ikromov, specializing in rice, grain and vegetables.

On November 15, 1937, Koreans forcibly resettled in Uzbekistan were mostly middling (11,932 people), Quyichirchiq (8,669 people), Yuqorichirchiq (1,814 people), Mirzachul (6,975 people), Bekabad (4,438 people), Chinoz (2,746 people), Qungot (2,746 people), Gurlan (5,799) districts: Samarkand (1,798 people), Bukhara (4,798 people 399 people), Fergana (1,104 people), Kokand (1,700 people), Namangan (1,269 people), Andijan (1,928 people).

From 1937 to 1945, these Koreans were not registered as special settlers, their passports included restrictions prohibiting them from going beyond Uzbekistan.

Koreans as special settlers on June 2, 1945, the people's commissar of internal affairs of the SSSR L. According to the order of Beria, registration is carried out, and all measures to strengthen the regime of residence are also applied to them.

The directive of the Ministry of internal affairs of the USSR of August 2, 1946 No. 196 defines issuing new passports without restrictions and formalizing them on a general basis on the place of residence to Koreans whose passports have restrictions for a period of 5 years and whose validity has already expired, including Koreans expelled from the Far East. However, the second directive of the Ministry of internal affairs of the SSSR No. 30 of March 3, 1947, in accordance with the procedure for applying Directive No. 196 of the Ministry of internal affairs of the USSR when issuing passports to Koreans, only Koreans residing in the republics of Central Asia were given passports, excluding Koreans living in border regions.

The same directive prohibited Koreans from living on the territory of the Far East (Buryat-Mongolian Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic, Primorsk and Khabarovsk territories, Chita region). And only in the second half of the 50s will these restrictions be removed, and the displaced Koreans will have the opportunity to return to their homeland.

Today, the Korean diaspora is an integral part of the multi-ethnic people in Uzbekistan and actively participates in all social and cultural events held in the Republic.

Dozens of representatives of the diaspora who have been awarded the title of Hero of Labor, including Kim Pen Hwa, the chairman of the "Polyarnaya zvezda" household, have been honored with this award twice. Independence provided new opportunities for the preservation of folk traditions, traditions and language and for greater solidarity of the diaspora. Founded in 1991, the Association of Korean cultural centers in Uzbekistan has 23 units operating in Tashkent City and Tashkent region, Andijan, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Navoi, Namangan, Syrdarya, Fergana, Khorezm regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

CONCLUSION

Due to the repressive policy pursued by Soviet authorities, even a small number of nations living on the territory of the country were unjustified from the territories in which they lived. As a result of this policy, along with other republics of the former Union, it was moved to Uzbekistan. Mass forced resettlement of Koreans in Uzbekistan along with other few nations begins in 1937-1938.

One of the blackest pages of the past is the mass death of people as a result of political repression of the 30s and 50s. Millions of people died in peacetime, and the fate of millions was disrupted by unjust sentences, prisons, camps, evictions. A lot has already been written about this tragedy of the human personality, but, of course, the topic is not over.

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